

APPLYING DIFFERENT TEACHING METHODS FOR ENHANCING THE READING SKILLS OF ELEMENTARY LEARNERS

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Annotation The main ordinary problem for an English learner is the trouble in comprehending the different reading texts they are reading. For this reason, how to enhance reading ability in learners withdraws more and more attention. This article has analyzed several reading skills and put forwards some suggestions for the development of English of elementary learners from personal experience, which may aid to enhance the learners' reading competence. For numerous elementary learners of foreign languages, reading is the skill that causes vast challenges. Most of the elementary learners attempt to reveal efficient methods to enhance their reading ability, but are still dissatisfied. Initial steps are to determine the meaning of reading and the types of necessary reading skills, that on the basis of this comprehending, search beneficial methods appropriately.

Key words: *Teaching, method, reading skill, elementary, learners, comprehension.*

Annotatsiya Ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilar uchun asosiy oddiy muammo - ular o'qiyotgan turli matnlarni tushunish qiyinligi. Shu sababli, o'quvchilarda o'qish qobiliyatini qanday oshirish kerakligi tobora ko'proq e'tiborni tortmoqda. Ushbu maqola bir nechta o'qish ko'nikmalarini tahlil qiladi va o'quvchilarning o'qish malakasini oshirishga yordam beradigan shaxsiy tajribadan boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ingliz tilini rivojlantirish bo'yicha ba'zi takliflarni ilgari suradi. Ko'plab boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari uchun o'qish - bu katta qiyinchiliklarga olib keladigan mahorat. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining aksariyati o'qish qobiliyatini oshirishning samarali usullarini ochib berishga harakat qilishadi, lekin hali ham norozi. Dastlabki bosqichlar o'qishning ma'nosini va kerakli o'qish ko'nikmalarining turlarini aniqlashdan iborat bo'lib, shundan so'ng ushbu tushunish asosida foydali usullarni to'g'ri izlash kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: *O'qitish, metod, o'qish malakasi, boshlang'ich sinf, o'quvchilar, tushunish.*

Аннотация Основной обычной проблемой для изучающих английский язык является проблема с пониманием различных текстов, которые они читают. По этой причине тому, как улучшить способность учащихся к чтению, уделяется все больше и больше внимания. В этой статье проанализированы некоторые навыки чтения и на основе личного опыта предложены некоторые предложения по развитию английского языка у учащихся начальных классов, которые могут помочь повысить их читательскую компетентность. Для многих людей, изучающих

иностранные языки на начальном этапе, чтение является навыком, вызывающим огромные трудности. Большинство учащихся начальной школы пытаются найти эффективные методы улучшения своих навыков чтения, но все равно остаются неудовлетворенными. Первыми шагами являются определение значения чтения и видов необходимых навыков чтения, а затем на основе этого понимания поиск соответствующих полезных методов.

Ключевые слова: *Обучение, метод, навык чтения, элементарный, учащиеся, понимание.*

In general speaking, reading is about comprehending written texts. However, comprehending is not ordinary. It is a complicated activity that includes both perception and thought. It involves two connected processes: word recognition and comprehension. Word recognition regarded as the process of perceiving how written symbols correspond to the spoken discourse.

Comprehension refers to the process of making sense of words, sentences and related text. [4,2020]One of the most evident, but mostly unnoticed facts about reading is that there are various types of reading skills. They especially consist of skimming, scanning, extensive and intensive reading. Skimming refers to reading quickly for the main idea; Scanning means to read fast to identify a specific piece of information; Extensive reading is reading a long text, mainly for pleasure with emphasis on its overall meaning; Intensive reading is reading a short text for details. It is obvious that making good improvements without the most correct reading style is not impossible. Hence, determining the reading style necessary in a specific reading situation should be chosen firstly to starting reading. There cannot be any words about efficient reading methods until this point is understood appropriately.

There are some teaching methods for enhancing reading skills of elementary learners:

Expanded vocabulary enhances comprehension

Most teachers consider that vocabulary is the key point of learning English well. The wider your vocabulary, the more efficiently you can learn language. It does not mean that you should take a dictionary wherever you go. Expanding vocabulary demands accumulating and utilizing words on a daily life. Ordinary methods to improve vocabulary as a part of daily basis involves reading everyday, utilizing contemporary sources like English language newspapers or the New York Times. Any kind of new words and expressions can be found in an Uzbek-English dictionary. Written new words and phrases in a notebook and created new sentences with them guarantees practice and causes comprehending of utilization. Revision of new words is significant for memory retention. When reviewing the new words, remember their utilization in the context. There may be some challenges initially, however tenacity will enhance comprehending and reading pleasure.

Enhancing comprehension by guessing the meaning from the context.

The context assists learners to predict the unfamiliar vocabulary [3:2000]. Initially, the reader can allude to the direct context and then to the wider context in which a word is revealed. The direct context is the sentence in which a word is revealed and sometimes the sentences instantly before and after this. The wider context can consist of other sentences and even other paragraphs in a text. Both forms of context can often provide crucial information which aid in inferring the meaning of unknown words. Context provides readers with large number of clues to understand the unknown words. The basic contextual clues involve definition, synonym, antonym, and example and cause-effect connection.

Enhancing your comprehension by recognizing patterns.

In the past, people have survived by determining patterns. Scientists state that it is nature of human to search for patterns in what they notice. Human brains are always attempting to make sense of the world around us, attempting to be suitable everything into some kind of recognizable shape that has meaning for us. There are four common patterns in a text [2,70:1991]. The first pattern is a listing connected ideas or examples. In this pattern, the writer’s basic idea is stated in the form of a generalization, followed by a list of supporting details. The second pattern is sequence. In this pattern, the writer’s basic ideas consist of a series events or steps that happen turn by turn. The third is comparison and contrast. In this pattern, the writer’s basic idea explains similarities or differences. The final pattern is cause-effect. When the basic idea is evolved by explaining one event or action causing another, the cause-effect pattern is represented. Causes and effects are part of daily basis, thus, this pattern is revealed mostly in history books, science texts, and novels.

Differentiating facts from opinion

Making distinction between facts and opinions will assist to obtain a deeper level of comprehension in reading. Facts can be utilized by a writer as a basis for convincing the readers that his idea is correct, they are common objective descriptions or statements; Opinions are mostly given to show the author’s attitudes or feeling about things, and so are subjective evaluations or predictions from both the character and the author. Generally, facts are directly connected to the evolution of the plot in a novel while opinions provide the author’s and character’s reflections.

Explaining the main idea of a passage.

Looking for the main idea. The main idea of a piece of writing is the essential point the author wants to make. It is said in a topic sentence, which sets the thesis, but also the tone, voice and style of the writing. Generally speaking, in the majority of reading text written for English readers it is located in the beginning of the writing, but may be repeated in the body and conclusion of the piece. Other language forms may change the position for the expression of the main idea. In addition, in most situations, the main idea is not often clearly given. It is more challenging to find a main idea when it is inferred or implied. Summarizing and restating the information in the passage assists interpret the main idea. Summarizing is taking wider selections of text and deducing them to their bare

essentials: the gist, the key ideas, and the main points. Summaries capture the main ideas and the important details. Summarizing mostly consist of key words, sentences and short passages. Experience represents that to obtain a better comprehension of the text, it is significant to ask questions.

Critical thinking is a good method to aid obtaining better comprehension of the text. Several writers ever directly tell you what to think, they attempt to inform you with enough data to enable readers to gain reasonable conclusion. The purpose of critical thinking in reading is to engage the reader in the reading activity more thoroughly.

Using the SQ3R strategy

SQ3R is a beneficial and crucial method in reading to understand written information. It assists to build a good construct of the subject, creating a framework for correct insertion of facts. Additionally, SQ3R allows readers to set learning goals and prompts the usage of revision techniques. The acronym SQ3R stands for the five sequential techniques readers should use to read a book. Scan the “S” means a short survey, ”Q” is question; the “3R” are read, recall and review. Survey means to scan the contents, introduction, and summaries to pick up initial overview of the text. Question means note any questions on the subject that come to mind, or mainly interest you. The first ”R” means read beneficial sections in detail attentively to corresponding points; the second R demands the reader to remember significant sections once they are read, separating the core facts or the important processes behind the subject, and then evaluate how other information corresponds. The third R asks the reader to review the reading text. This review can be done by re-reading the document, by expanding notes, or by discussing the material with other readers. Especially efficient method of reviewing information is to teach someone else. By utilizing SQ3R to actively read a document, the maximum profit is achieved from the reading time.

Activate background knowledge

One of the biggest anticipators of reading comprehension is prior knowledge. Readers understand better when they actively think about and practice their knowledge of the topic and their own experiences. Prior knowledge can be utilized to improve reading comprehension, especially when dealing with unknown topics. Here are some suggestions to use prior knowledge whenever required. Before reading, consider any connected knowledge of the topic. While reading, activate other memories, personal experiences and any other kinds of data connected to the details of the reading material. After reading, search further at the library or on the Internet to identify answers to the questions. Activating prior knowledge is significant reading method for better comprehension.

Enhance comprehension by enhancing grammatical understanding

Grammar is also important and the most complicated part of English language learning. It can be considered as most students’ weakest point. English grammar is significant and beneficial tool in reading process. It is a combination of the phonics and holistic argument. In order to comprehend the whole text, the parts of reading must be

seen. Grammar is essential tool mainly for weak readers to assist them to comprehend ideas. Hence, it is significant to learn grammar and have a strong grammatical basis. Grammar can be studied in small steps, and demands general practice. Study the basics of one grammar point, then move on to another point. When readers are comfortable with the basics, they can move forward to learn the details. Grammatical skills increase comprehension of readers, and are worth for studying.

Improve comprehension by understanding

When a learner overhears a part of a conversation and attempts to imagine what it was about is an ordinary usage of making inferences [1,35:1997]. Sometimes the topic of a text may not be stated anywhere directly, in the reading, making the search for clues and try to predict what the passage is about. The authors of novels, stories or plays often do not explain everything about characters or situations. The reader must deduce the author’s meaning from the descriptions or the dialogues.

Improve comprehension by forming good reading habits.

Many people desire they read more, as it can assist improve knowledge and be more prosperous in a diverse of fields. The following suggestions can assist to boost reading ability: to have reading material close by - bathroom, briefcase and bed; setting a reading goal; determining how much time can be spent on reading, or how many books to read over time. Reading groups and books can help reading goals and allow discussion groups for further comprehension. Reading includes specific skills, knowledge and common sense. By analyzing and generalizing the skills in the process of reading, these skills and methods can be transferred easily to struggling readers.

Mostly reading skills for elementary learners, such as how to deal with the unknown words, how to find the main idea, how to critically read, and how to understand better by different kinds of materials can be developed by following the methods mentioned above. Implementing all above mentioned methods for improving reading skills of elementary learners in the teaching process will be beneficial.

The basic common problem for an English learner is the drawbacks in comprehending the diverse reading materials which are read by them. Hence, how to improve reading comprehension skills of learners becoming more and more grabbing attention point.

There are some strategies for solving any kind of problems which related reading comprehension. In the first chapter of this course paper there were revealed most two strategies that improve reading comprehension of elementary level learners. One of them is SQ3R strategy that can be used to increase the students’ reading skills and assist students’ difficulties in comprehending the text. The students have to utilize their main knowledge or background knowledge and recent obtained knowledge in order to apply SQ3R efficiently. This strategy can also help the teacher to avoid monotonous environment by giving diverse exercises. Thus, it can be said that using SQ3R strategy can give solution for the students to enhance their reading ability and also assist them in comprehending any kind of text. SQ3R is a simple and easy strategy to implement in the

lessons in order to make more active as well as all students at the same time communicating with each other, improve their reading comprehension successfully via authentic piece of texts, because elementary learners can understand and comprehend authentic materials related to all aspects of life, thus teachers prefer to implement SQ3R strategy in improving learners reading comprehension effectively. Furthermore, there are several teaching methods for enhancing reading skills of elementary learners, such as Expanded vocabulary enhances comprehension; Enhancing comprehension by guessing the meaning from the context; Enhancing your comprehension by recognizing patterns; Differentiating facts from opinion ; Explaining the main idea of a passage; Using the SQ3R strategy; Activate background knowledge; Enhance comprehension by enhancing grammatical understanding; Improve comprehension by understanding; Improve comprehension by forming good reading habits. Mainly reading skills for elementary learners, such as how to deal with the unknown words, how to find the main idea, how to critically read, and how to understand better by various types of sources can be improved according to above mentioned methods. Implementing all these methods for developing reading skills of elementary learners in the teaching process will be useful.

To conclude, applying strategies like SQ3R ,Think-aloud also, some useful tips and methods for improving reading comprehension of elementary learners is worth in teaching English classrooms.

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